

Ultrathin, Transparent, Thermally-insulated, and Energy-efficient Flexible Window Using Coatable Chiral-nematic Liquid Crystal Polymer

Amid Ranjkesh ^{a,b,*}, Tae-Hoon Yoon ^{a,*}

^a *Department of Electronics Engineering, Pusan National University, Busan 46241, Republic of Korea.*

^b *Condensed Matter Department, J. Stefan Institute, Jamova 39, Ljubljana, Slovenia*

E-mail: amidranjkesh@gmail.com, thyoon@pusan.ac.kr

Abstract

Transparent windows that insulate infrared (IR) light entering indoor spaces promise to reduce energy consumption. However, a long-standing challenge for an energy-efficient window is achieving compactness and flexibility simultaneously. In this paper, we report the fabrication of a transparent, flexible, ultrathin, and thermally-insulated IR reflector using a coatable chiral-nematic liquid crystal polymer and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) as an alignment layer. PVA is transparent, biocompatible, thermostable, noncorrosive, and cost-effective. The fabricated IR reflector shows high optical transparency (~91%) and low haze (~9.8%) values in the visible spectrum of light. Moreover, it significantly reduces greenhouse gas emissions by preventing energy consumption for cooling systems and lighting in indoor spaces; specifically, it reduces electricity consumption in indoor spaces for lighting and cooling systems under hot weather conditions. To demonstrate the mechanical stability of the fabricated reflector, many mechanical, flexibility, and bending stability tests were conducted. The results show that our proposed IR reflector is a potential candidate for designing desirable shapes for many applications, such as anti-IR devices and energy-efficient windows, for achieving significant environmental and economic benefits.

KEYWORDS: liquid crystal; chiral-nematic liquid crystal polymer; liquid crystal polymer; flexible application; thermally insulated window

Introduction

At present, conventional residential building windows are composed of glass. Such glass windows are associated with long-standing challenges, such as fragility and energy leakage [1]. More than 50% of the total energy required for air conditioning and heating in buildings and indoor spaces is spent on compensating for the poor thermal insulation of conventional glass [1]. The fabrication of a thermally-insulated near-infrared (NIR) film, which can cut off the NIR wavelengths of sunlight, is a promising approach for addressing heating costs, reducing energy consumption, and preventing global warming [2,3] because sunlight is a leading cause of heat generation in buildings, particularly in summer and hot weather conditions. If a NIR reflector can shield from the heat and still maintain appropriate visible light transparency in the windows, it would be desirable.

Fragile architectural glass curves are another challenging issue in residential buildings, resulting in glass breaking upon sudden impressions. As windows play a significant role in the esthetics of modern buildings, the fabrication of flexible glass that solves the issues of fragility and cuts off the NIR wavelengths of sunlight would be desirable. Flexible smart windows have already been fabricated using two flexible plastic substrates, such as indium tin oxide and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) [4–6]. The use of spacers to maintain the thickness and cell gap between the two plastics is, however, a challenge. Moreover, owing to the fluid nature of the filling material, the use of two substrates is another challenge. Therefore, it would be highly advantageous to use a facile method to employ materials that appropriately attach to the surface of plastics with outstanding optical performance without changing the material's performance and deteriorating the glass performance during bending. Among the materials with the above-mentioned properties, chiral reactive mesogen (CRM) is a fascinating example. CRMs can be readily converted to polymer films by irradiation with ultraviolet (UV) light. Moreover, CRMs have many noteworthy

features, including chiral properties, high transparency, coating capability, excellent durability, and high mechanical flexibility [7–9]. Furthermore, they have right- or left-handed chirality, thereby demonstrating a pitch-selective reflection of the incident light [10–14]. Accordingly, we can obtain a chiral nematic liquid crystal polymer which are also known as cholesteric liquid crystal (CLC) polymer using both the right- and left-handed CRMs in a plastic substrate with a wide reflection band in the NIR region.

In the fabrication of a flexible and transparent infrared (IR) reflector, the choice of alignment material is very important. The alignment material should be optically transparent, thermostable, strong enough to withstand mechanical stress, and cost-effective. Although polyimide has been widely used as an alignment material for flexible substrates, it has several drawbacks, such as being required in large quantities, requiring high temperatures of over 200 °C for imidization processes, requiring a rubbing process, being costly, and possessing high haze [15]. Moreover, the polyimide alignment layers for liquid crystals (LCs) often do not maintain the alignment state and have a low anchoring strength, short durability, and high pretilt angle [15]. In addition, the rubbing process generates defects in the LC alignment. To overcome these drawbacks, polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) can be an excellent alternative owing to its high optical transmission, biocompatibility, thermostability, non-corrosiveness, low cost, low-temperature process, and absence of alignment defects [15–17]. A uniform homogeneous alignment of CRMs and other LCs can be achieved with this material [15]. Remarkably, PVA exhibits high elasticity and resistance to mechanical stress. Thus, it would serve as an ideal alignment layer for flexible reflectors. Moreover, it has a high anchoring strength with LCs and a small pretilt angle in many LC devices [18, 19].

In this study, a thin, transparent, flexible, and thermally-insulated energy-efficient window using a coatable CLC polymer and PVA as an alignment layer between the coating layers was fabricated. The proposed NIR polymer reflector successfully reflected approximately 90% of the incoming IR light. By adjusting the PVA concentration, we achieved an IR reflector with high transparency of visible light. To check the mechanical stability of the IR reflector, various flexibility and bending stability tests, such as for the radius-of-curvature limit, bending cycle, and lifetime of the film, were carried out. The proposed reflector can be employed over a wide temperature range because the polymer network in the CLC film exhibits a permanent solid helical structure along with the temperature-independent pitch length. Moreover, the reflection band was precisely controlled in the reflector through the experimental procedure, and controlling the temperature was not necessary. Overall, our transparent and flexible thermally-insulated energy-efficient IR film can open avenues to achieve significant environmental and economic benefits.

2 Experimental work

2.1 Materials

We used a left-handed chiral reactive mesogen (RM) (HCM-006, HCCH, China) with a helical twisting power (HTP) of $57 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$, right-handed chiral RM (LC-756, HTP = $76 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$, BASF), monoacrylate monomer 4-Methoxybenzoic acid 4-(6-acryloyloxy-hexyloxy) phenyl ester (ST03866, SYNTHON), diacrylate monomer RM-257 (BASF), ultraviolet (UV) light absorber (2-hydroxyphenyl-benzophenones, Chimassorb 81, BASF), and photoinitiator (Irgacure 651, BASF). All the materials were used as obtained without further purification. Based on the HTP of the chiral RMs, two different CLC mixtures were prepared to fabricate IR reflectors: a left-handed CLC mixture including RM-257/ ST03866/ HCM-006/Chimassorb 81/Irgacure-651 (weight ratio 73/23/3/0.5/0.5) and a right-handed CLC mixture, which consisted of RM-257/ST03866/ LC-756/

Chimassorb 81/Irgacure-651 (weight ratio 73/22/4/0.5/0.5). To build a UV intensity gradient across the film thickness, we added a UV light absorber (Chimassorb 81, BASF) to the CLC mixture. Moreover, this absorber stabilizes the polymer mixture properly, as confirmed previously [4, 12]. Figure 1 shows the chemical structures of materials used in this study.

(a) HCM-006 (HCCH China)

(b) LC-756 (BASF)

(c) ST03866 (SYNTHON)

(d) RM-257 (BASF)

(e) Chimassorb 81 (BASF)

(e) Irgacure 651 (BASF)

(f) Polyvinyl alcohol

Figure 1 Chemical structures of materials used in this study.

2.2 Sample preparation and experimental procedure

A PET film was cleaned and spin-coated with a 4 wt% aqueous PVA solution (Sigma-Aldrich Chemical). Subsequently, the film was cured for 30 min at 100 °C. A doctor blade coating process for the mixtures was performed for the film at an appropriate speed to coat the mixture. Then, the samples were exposed to UV light (Newport, Co., LTD), which was emitted from a mercury arc lamp (Osram HBO 103 W/2) with an intensity of 0.1 mW/cm² under a nitrogen atmosphere, for 30 min at 50 °C and then post-cured under high UV flood exposure with an intensity of 20 mW/cm² for 10 min. To fabricate a super-reflectivity flexible film, a roll-to-roll laminating method was employed to assemble the two oppositely-handed CLC films. The left- and right-handed CLC films were firmly combined to fabricate a flexible super-reflective film. Figure 2 shows a schematic of the fabrication process. In our approach, two different broadband CLC films with opposite-handed reflections were directly coated to fabricate a superimposed super-reflective and broadband polymer bilayer.

The transmission spectra were measured using a spectrometer (Flame-NIR Spectrometer, Ocean Optics). To measure the surface texture of the film and PVA layer thickness, we used a three-dimensional (3D) optical surface profiler (Nanosurface Profiler NV-E1000, Nano System Co., Ltd.). The thickness of the film was 36.4 μm.

To demonstrate the optical performance of the fabricated polymer IR reflector, the specular transmittance and haze were measured using a haze meter (HM-65W, Murakami Color Research Laboratory) after bending the CLC films at particular periods. The total transmittance (T_t) is the sum of the specular transmittance (T_s) and diffuse transmittance (T_d). Thus, the haze (H) can be calculated as $H = T_d/T_t$ [20–22]. The experimental setup for evaluating the optical performance of the fabricated polymer CLC film is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2 Schematic illustration of the fabrication of transparent, flexible, and thin polymer CLC IR film using sequential layer-by-layer of right- and left-handed CRMs superimposed on each other along with a photo-polymerization process and PVA alignment layer.

3 Results and discussion

The fabricated polymer CLC film showed a reflection peak centered near 1128 nm before polymerization. After the polymerization, a broadband reflective film was obtained with a bandwidth of 284 nm. The broadband reflection of the polymer CLC film can be explained by the diacrylate forms of chiral RMs so that the concentration of chiral RMs is the highest in the UV-

exposed area at the top side of films. Because of the high UV intensity, the chiral RMs at the top side of the film polymerize faster than those at the bottom.

Figure 3 Schematic view of the setup for evaluation of the optical performance of fabricated polymer CLC film.

The diffusion of chiral RMs from the bottom to the top side and their nonuniform distributions can lead to a pitch gradient throughout the film's thickness [23–26]. Consequently, the pitch gradient within the film can result in broadband reflection. Moreover, the reflection bandwidth $\Delta\lambda$ in CLCs is highly dependent on and is determined by the birefringence Δn of the LC [27–30]. Because of the low value of Δn in the LCs, $\Delta\lambda$ of the CLC films is generally too small to facilitate the reflection of a massive amount of IR light. To broaden the $\Delta\lambda$ of CLC films, we used a UV light absorber (Chimassorb 81) to absorb UV radiation and generate a UV-intensity gradient in CLC films. That is, UV light absorption creates a UV-intensity gradient within the CLC mixture upon UV irradiation, as reported previously [23–26]. In particular, the UV light absorber prevents degradation of the substrate, robustly stabilizes the polymer film and improves the durability of

the polymeric film against external forces [4, 12]. Figure 4(a) shows the transmission spectra of the polymer CLC film with and without the UV light absorber. Broadband reflection in the NIR wavelength was observed in the fabricated film. In addition, low-intensity UV exposure followed by high-intensity UV exposure was performed for polymerization of the polymer CLC film. As shown in Figure 4(a), the fabricated film exhibits a broadband reflection of unpolarized IR light ranging from 870 to 1330 nm. Therefore, the broadband IR reflector can reflect most of the incident IR energy when it is coated over the window.

The UV illumination time is a fundamental factor for achieving broadband reflection [31, 32]. Figure 4(b) shows that for a short UV irradiation time, a narrower band of reflection can be determined for the CLC film. Because of the lower UV irradiation time, no appropriate pitch gradient is formed within the film. However, under a long UV irradiation time, the UV light absorber and CRMs have adequate opportunities to move to the top side of the film to form a pitch gradient. The results of the center wavelengths and bandwidths of the polymer CLC films at different UV-curing times are shown in Figures 4(b).

To obtain high anchoring strength and the appropriate optical performance in the flexible IR reflectors, concentrations of PVA as an alignment layer were tested in our experiments because the variation in the PVA layer thickness controls the surface anchoring strength [15]. However, upon the PVA layer thickness being increased, the optical properties of our fabricated film changed. Our results showed that at high PVA concentrations (e.g., 6 wt%), higher haze and lower transmittance values were observed in the IR film. Notably, the outstanding optical performance was achieved for a PVA concentration of 4 wt% and a layer thickness of 98 nm. To analyze the

effect of PVA concentration on the optical performance of the fabricated polymer IR reflector, the specular transmittance and haze were measured at different PVA concentrations.

Figure 4 (a) Transmission spectra of the polymer CLC film fabricated using the UV light absorber and without the absorber for 30-min UV light irradiation. (b) Center reflection wavelengths and bandwidths of the polymer CLC films at different UV-curing times. (c) Total transmittance and haze values of polymer CLC film at different PVA concentrations. (d) Photographs of the fabricated CLC polymer films at different PVA concentrations demonstrating high transparency of the films at low PVA 4% wt.

Figure 4(c) presents the total transmittance and haze values of the polymer CLC IR film at different PVA concentrations. For 4 wt% PVA, the fabricated polymer IR reflector shows excellent optical performance. The values of total transmittance and haze of the fabricated IR reflector at 4 wt% PVA were 89.7 and 7.6%, respectively. These values confirmed that the fabricated IR reflector was transparent to visible light when the film was coated over a window. To compare the

optical properties of PVA and polyimide, we prepared an IR film using polyimide as an alignment layer with the same CRM mixture. The process for fabricating the IR film using polyimide is described in the Supporting Information. The total transmittance and haze spectra in the IR film using a polyimide layer are shown in Figure S1. The total transmittance and haze values for this type of IR film were 76.8 and 9.5%, respectively. Consequently, PVA exhibited better optical performance and higher transparency than those of polyimide an alignment layer. Figure 4(d) shows photographs of the fabricated CLC polymer films at different PVA concentrations. High transparency was observed at a PVA concentration of 4 wt%.

We expect that the proposed reflective IR film will be promising for potential applications. For a broad application of the fabricated film, several tests, including temperature effects and mechanical stability tests, need to be analyzed. Moreover, the proposed IR reflector is temperature-independent because of the excellent stability of the Bragg reflection band at elevated temperatures. To confirm this feature, transmission measurements of the CLC films were carried out at temperatures ranging from 25 to 55 °C. The effect of temperature on the films was tested using a Mettler FP82 hot-stage controlled by a Mettler FP90. The center wavelength of the reflection spectra remained approximately intact with a little shift, which approximately implies the same reflection band over the temperature range, as shown in Figures 5(a). Therefore, the fabricated polymer IR film is temperature-independent and can be operated under nearly all global weather conditions without significantly affecting the performance of the CLC polymer film.

To check the mechanical stability, many tests, such as for the radius-of-curvature limit, bending cycle, and lifetime of the polymer CLC film, were carried out. To perform a radius-of-curvature limit test, we wrapped the film on three cylindrical holders with different radii (e.g. 30,

50, and 70 mm) at room temperature (25 °C) for 24 h. Subsequently, the film was detached from the cylinder to analyze its transmission characteristics. The fabricated polymer CLC film returned to its original state without any performance degradation (e.g., cracks or wrinkles) during repeated bending fatigue tests. Figure 5(b) shows that the peak wavelength of the fabricated CLC film exhibited a similar performance even after the bending test. In the next test, the CLC film was bent and returned to its initial state, as shown in the inset of Figure 5(c). The film was subjected to a bending radius of 50 mm in the concave state after multiple bending cycles. As confirmed in Figure 5(c), the central peak wavelengths of the films were approximately the same, and no significant performance degradation was observed after the IR film was bent. To measure the lifetime of the polymer IR film, the center wavelengths in the concave mode are shown as a function of time for 24 h at room temperature (25 °C). Figure 5(d) reveals that the center wavelengths did not change even after bending for a long time.

Figure 5 (a) Center reflection wavelengths of the polymer CLC films at different temperatures. (b) Center reflection wavelengths of the polymer CLC films for different bending radii of 30, 50, and 70 mm, bent for 24 h at room temperature (25 °C). Inset shows a schematic of the bending test. (c) Center reflection wavelengths of the polymer CLC film under bending radius of 50 mm in the concave state after multiple bending. Inset shows a schematic of the cycling mode. (d) Center reflection wavelengths of the polymer CLC film as a function of time to measure the lifetime of the polymer CLC film in the concave mode for 24 h at room temperature (25 °C).

To study the influence of bending on the performance of flexible reflectors, the transmission spectra of the flexible polymer CLC reflector were analyzed at two different curvatures, called concave and convex states. The transmission spectra of CLC reflectors under different curvatures and their schematic states are shown in Figures 6(a) and 6(b) for the convex and concave states, respectively. The transmission spectra for the polymer CLC reflector show

that the flexural central reflections were maintained in the range of 1128 nm for the convex state and 1116 nm for the concave state at 25 °C in the case of bending under different curvatures. However, a slight difference in the transmitted intensity could be observed because of the different angles of the incident light. Indeed, a small blue-shift tuning in the reflection band in the film can be explained by $\lambda_o = n p_o \cos \theta$, where p_o is the CLC pitch length, and n is the average refractive index defined by $n = (n_e + n_o)/2$. Here, n_o and n_e are the ordinary and extraordinary refractive indices, respectively [33–36]. In the above equation, θ is the incident angle of light. Because of the curved surface of the polymer CLC film, different incident angles were established while the incident light passed through the film. Therefore, slight blue-shift tuning in the reflection can occur in the central reflection band.

If the fabricated polymer CLC IR film is used as an energy-saving smart window, it will undergo long exposure to UV light emitted from the sun. Prolonged UV exposure causes significant damage to the surface of the IR film, degrades the mechanical properties, and shortens their service life. Thus, optical performance of the film should be evaluated against high UV exposure. Figure 6(c) shows optical performance of our fabricated polymer CLC film for different UV light exposure times. The total transmittance and haze values of the fabricated films were stable over a long period of UV light exposure with an intensity of 10 mW/cm². Therefore, our fabricated polymer CLC film is robust against UV light from the sun, and it can be employed in the facades of buildings as an energy-saving smart window.

To better analyze the fabricated polymer CLC film for an energy-saving window, we analyzed the thermal control property of the film by fabricating a test box house without a solar shading system with a size of 3 cm × 3 cm × 3 cm. A thermocouple thermometer was placed in

the house to monitor the temperature. In addition, we collected the temperature every 5 min from 0 to 60 min. The test box was then placed under direct sunlight. Sunlight can penetrate through the polymer CLC window and affect the indoor temperature of house. Figure 6(d) shows the temperature in the house built with the polymer CLC reflector films, which increased to 40.2 °C. To make a comparison, a house was built with conventional glass as a reference, whose indoor temperature increased to 61.5 °C. The results indicate that the indoor temperature can be controlled by blocking or transmitting NIR light by the fabricated polymer CLC reflector. Therefore, this reflector appropriately reflects the IR light so that it can effectively prevent a significant amount of solar heat from entering the house. Moreover, an experiment was conducted in early spring when the solar emission was moderate. A significantly higher temperature difference can be expected when a similar experiment was performed during the summer. The heat insulation test establishes the viability of using the proposed polymer IR reflector to design highly efficient energy-saving windows and facades particularly in hot weather conditions.

Figure 6 Transmission spectra of the polymer CLC film at (a) convex and (b) concave states. (c) Total transmittance and haze values of the polymer CLC film at different UV light exposure times. (d) Temperature measurement in terms of time in the miniature house covered with a polymer CLC film.

Conclusion

In this study, we employed a facile method to fabricate a thermally-insulated and transparent polymer reflector to control IR reflection selectively. The fabricated reflector demonstrates a wide reflection band, thin, flexible, and highly transparent in visible light, allowing the visible light to be transmitted into the indoor spaces. The proposed reflector appropriately reflects the solar IR energy with a low optical haze, high transparency, and without disturbing the visible solar radiation.

The proposed reflector possesses the maximum freedom to provide irregular shapes, high flexibility, rollability, and mechanical deformation without detrimental effects on the desirable appearance or performance for various applications.

The transparent polymer CLC reflector is a thermal insulator that can reject IR light in indoor spaces, cars, and buildings. Therefore, indoor temperature was maintained at a comfortable level without cooling systems. Consequently, a considerable reduction in the energy consumption can be obtained. A lower indoor temperature was confirmed by conducting a heat insulation test on the proposed film. Accordingly, a substantial effect on the indoor temperature can be achieved in living and working spaces by reducing significant energy consumption. We expect our proposed transparent IR film to be employed in various large-scale applications because it offers endless possibilities as a potential reflector in anti-IR devices, energy-efficient windows, and facades of modern buildings without stinting desirable shapes.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the National Research Foundation of Korea (No. 2020R1A2C1006464). This result is part of a project that has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program (Grant agreement No. 884928-LOGOS).

References

- 1 Pérez-Lombard, L.; Ortiz, J.; Pout, C. A review on buildings energy consumption information, *Energy Build.* **2008**, *40*, 394–398.
- 2 Mitov, M. Cholesteric liquid crystals with a broad light reflection band. *Adv. Mater.* **2012**, *24*, 6260–6276.

3 Khandelwal, H.; Loonen, R. C. G. M.; Hensen, J. L. M.; Schenning, A. P. H. J.; Debije, M. G. Application of broadband infrared reflector based on cholesteric liquid crystal polymer bilayer film to windows and its impact on reducing the energy consumption in buildings. *J. Mater. Chem.* **2014**, *2*, 14622–14627.

4 Ranjkesh, A. and Yoon, T.H, Fabrication of a single-substrate flexible thermoresponsive cholesteric liquid-crystal film with wavelength tunability. *ACS Appl. Matter. Inter.*, **2019**, *11*, 26314-26322.

5 Kim, D.Y., Lee, K.M., White, T.J., Jeong, K.U. Cholesteric liquid crystal paints: in situ photopolymerization of helicoidally stacked multilayer nanostructures for flexible broadband mirrors. *NPG Asia Materials.* **2018**, *10*,1061.

6 Li, Y.; Liu, Y. J.; Dai, H. T.; Zhang, X. H.; Luo, D.; Sun, X. W. Flexible cholesteric films with super-reflectivity and high stability based on a multi-layer helical structure. *J. Mater. Chem. C*, **2017**, *5*, 10828–10833.

7 Balamurugan, R, Liu, J.-H, A Review of the fabrication of photonic band gap materials based on cholesteric liquid crystals. *React. Funct. Polym.* **2016**, *105*, 9–34.

8 Bahr, C.; Kitzerow, H. S. *Chirality in Liquid Crystals*; Springer: Heidelberg, 2001.

9 Davies D.J., Vaccaro A.R., Morris S.M., Herzer N., Schenning A.P., Bastiaansen, C.W. A printable optical time-temperature integrator based on shape memory in a chiral nematic polymer network. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2013**, *23*, 2723-2727.

10 Ostwald, P.; Pieranski, P. *Nematic and Cholesteric Liquid Crystals*; CRC: Boca Raton, **2005**.

11 Mitov, M.; Dessaud, N. Going beyond the reflectance limit of cholesteric liquid crystals. *Nat. Mater.* **2006**, *5*, 361–364.

12 Ranjkesh A., Yoon T.H. Thermal and electrical wavelength tuning of Bragg reflection with ultraviolet light absorbers in polymer-stabilized cholesteric liquid crystals. *J. Mat. Chem. C.* **2018**;6(45):12377-85.

13 Kim, J.; Kim, H.; Kim, S.; Choi, S.; Jang, W.; Kim, J.; Lee, J.-H. Broadening the reflection bandwidth of polymer-stabilized cholesteric liquid crystal via a reactive surface coating layer. *Appl. Opt.* **2017**, *56*, 5731–5735.

14 Wu, P.C., Wu, G.W., Timofeev, I.V., Zyryanov, V.Y. and Lee, W. Electro-thermally tunable reflective colors in a self-organized cholesteric helical superstructure. *Photonics Res.* **2018**, *6*, 1094-1100.

15 Cui, Y.; Zola, R.S.; Yang, Y.C; Yang, D.K. Alignment layers with variable anchoring strengths from Polyvinyl Alcohol. *J. Appl. Phys.*, **2012**, *111*, 063520.

16 Petkovšek, R.; Čopič, M.; Pirš, J., Influence of alignment layer thickness on ferroelectric liquid-crystal structure. *J. Appl. Phys.*, **2006**, *99*, 044103.

- 17 Wei, X., Hong, S.C., Zhuang, X., Goto, T. and Shen, Y.R., Nonlinear optical studies of liquid crystal alignment on a rubbed polyvinyl alcohol surface. *Phys. Rev. E*, **2000**, *62*, 5160.
- 18 Nechifor, C.D., Postolache, M., Albu, R.M., Barzic, A.I. and Dorohoi, D.O., Induced birefringence of rubbed and stretched polyvinyl alcohol foils as alignment layers for nematic molecules. *Polym. Advan. Technol.*, **2019**, *30*, 2143-2152.
- 19 Ishihara, S. and Mizusaki, M. Alignment control technology of liquid crystal molecules. *J. Soc. Inf. Disp*, **2020**, *28*, 44-74.
- 20 Huh, J.W., Seo, J.H., Oh, S.W., Kim, S.H. and Yoon, T.H. Tristate switching of a liquid-crystal cell among initial transparent, haze-free dark, and high-haze dark states. *J. Mol. Liq.*, **2019**, *281*, 81-85.
- 21 Huh, J.W., Yu, B.H., Heo, J., Ji, S.M. and Yoon, T.H. Technologies for display application of liquid crystal light shutters. *Mol. Cryst. Liq. Cryst.*, 2017, *644*, 120-129.
- 22 Huh, J.W., Oh, S.W., Seo, J.H., Sohn, H.J. and Yoon, T.H., Filtering of yellow light in a liquid-crystal light shutter for higher color contrast and reduced glare. *J. Mol. Liq.*, **2020**, 114846.
- 23 Broer, D.J., Lub, J. and Mol, G.N. Wide-band reflective polarizers from cholesteric polymer networks with a pitch gradient. *Nature*, **1995**, *378*, 467-469.
- 24 Relaix, S., Bourgerette, C. and Mitov, M. Broadband reflective cholesteric liquid crystalline gels: volume distribution of reflection properties and polymer network in relation with the geometry of the cell photopolymerization. *Liq. Cryst.* **2007**, *34*, 1009-1018.
- 25 Bian, Z., Li, K., Huang, W, Cao, H., Yang, H. Characteristics of selective reflection of chiral nematic liquid crystalline gels with a nonuniform pitch distribution, *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, **2007**, *91*, 201908.
- 26 Wang, F., Li, K., Song, P., Wu, X., Cao, H. and Yang, H. Photoinduced pitch gradients and the reflection behaviour of the broadband films: influence of dye concentration, light intensity, temperature and monomer concentration. *Liq. Cryst.* **2012**, *39*, 707-714.
- 27 Hsiao, Y.C., Yang, Z.H., Shen, D. and Lee, W. Red, green, and blue reflections enabled in an electrically tunable helical superstructure. *Adv. Opt. Mater*, **2018**, *6*, 1701128.
- 28 Kim, H., Kim, J., Kim, S., Kim, J. and Lee, J.H., Effect of the ratio between monoacrylate and diacrylate reactive mesogen on the transmission spectrum of polymer-stabilized cholesteric liquid crystal. *Opt. Mater. Express*, **2018**, *8*, 97-104.
- 29 Mitov M, Cholesteric liquid crystals in living matter. *Soft Matter*, **2017**, *13*, 4176-4209, and references therein.
- 30 Guo, J., Wu, H., Chen, F., Zhang, L., He W., Yang, H., Wei J. Fabrication of multi-pitched photonic structure in cholesteric liquid crystals based on a polymer template with helical structure. *J. Mater. Chem.* **2010**, *20*, 4094-102.

- 31 Duan, M.Y., Cao, H., Wu, Y., Li, E.L., Wang, H.H., Wang, D., Yang, Z., He, W.L. and Yang, H., Broadband reflection in polymer stabilized cholesteric liquid crystal films with stepwise photopolymerization. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, **2017**, *19*, 2353-2358.
- 32 Hu, W., Chen, M., Wang, Q., Zhang, L., Yuan, X., Chen, F. and Yang, H., Broadband Reflection in Polymer-Stabilized Cholesteric Liquid Crystals via Thiol–Acrylate Chemistry. *Angew. Chem.*, **2019**, *131*, 6770-6774.
- 33 Khandelwal, H., van Heeswijk, E.P., Schenning, A.P. and Debije, M.G. Paintable temperature-responsive cholesteric liquid crystal reflectors encapsulated on a single flexible polymer substrate. *J. Mater. Chem. C*, **2019**, *7*, 7395-7398.
- 34 Van Heeswijk, E.P., Meerman, T., de Heer, J., Grossiord, N. and Schenning, A.P. Paintable encapsulated body-temperature-responsive photonic reflectors with arbitrary shapes. *ACS Appl. Poly. Mater.*, **2019**, *12*, 3407–3412.
- 35 Ryabchun, A. and Bobrovsky, A. Cholesteric liquid crystal materials for tunable diffractive optics. *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **2018**, *6*, 1800335.
- 36 McConney, M.E., Tondiglia, V.P., Hurtubise, J.M., White, T.J. and Bunning, T.J. Photoinduced hyper-reflective cholesteric liquid crystals enabled via surface initiated photopolymerization. *Chem. Comm.*, **2011**, *47*, 505-507.